

From Software to Living Data

Sustaining African Red Slip Ware

Knowledge beyond the ARS3D project

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image created using Google's Gemini

LEIBNIZ - ZENTRUM
FÜR ARCHÄOLOGIE

From Kiln to Context | Ghent | Belgium

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leiza.de

Digital archaeology often relies on project-specific software that becomes obsolete soon after funding ends

Well-curated, semantically structured data can mature over time and enable reuse, reinterpretation, and cross-domain integration

Software is like Fish, Data is like Wine!

Therefore, we argue for data-centric sustainability rather than long-term reliance on project-specific software

ARS3D digitised African Red Slip Ware in 3D and documented it using a **CIDOC CRM**-based semantic model

Core outputs were published as *Linked Open Data* on Zenodo, ensuring persistence, citability, and openness

Key entities were curated in Wikidata, allowing ARS knowledge to persist as community-maintained data

African Red Slip Ware digital ARS3D - The Project

slides are based on

Thiery, F., & Mees, A. W. (2024). Sharing Linked Open Data with domain-specific data-driven community hubs – archaeology.link in NFDI4Objects. *Archeologia e Calcolatori*, 35(2), 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.08>

Thiery, F., Karmacharya, A., & Rokohl, L. (2022). Semantic modelling and publishing African Red Slip Ware as Linked Data. *Squirrel Papers*, 4(4), No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7361811>

Thiery, F., Veller, J., Raddatz, L., Rokohl, L., Boochs, F., & Mees, A. W. (2023). A Semi-Automatic Semantic- Model-Based Comparison Workflow for Archaeological Features on Roman Ceramics. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 12(4), 167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi12040167>

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Federal Ministry
of Education
and Research

Römisch-Germanisches
Zentralmuseum
Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut
für Archäologie

R | G | Z | M

The German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) funded the African Red Slip Ware digital (ARS3D) Project 2018-2021

Object: © LEIZA | Photo: © Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg

Currently in the storage, the museum will open soon again...

- 325 objects, relief-decorated ceramic, distinguished by a thick-orange red slip
 - n = 271: African Red Slip Ware objects
 - n = 54: manufacturing objects
 - n = 157: bowl
 - n = 64: dish
 - n = 27: lamp
 - n = 7: plate
 - n = 6: jug
- mainly produced approx. 3 AD - 6 AD, North Africa, Tunisia
- ARS at LEIZA: private collections or that were acquired on the art market (see [Thiery et al. 2023](#))

0.39675

0.39450

0.41399

0.39676

0.39780

Objects: © LEIZA | Photos: © Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg

African Red Slip Ware used in ARS3D from the LEIZA/RGZM collection

Article

A Semi-Automatic Semantic-Model-Based Comparison Workflow for Archaeological Features on Roman Ceramics

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At the RGZM, the acquisition of ARS started in 1913, when a vessel [106] (p. 124) [18] (O.7046, Hayes form type 75) was bought from an Italian antiquarian. Roughly a third of the RGZM collection was, in the 1970s, obtained from a previously private collection that belonged to the Dutch archaeologist Jan Willem Salomonsen [107] (pp.17–21) [108] (p. 291), [109]. While “Unfortunately, there is only limited information on the survey campaigns of Salomonson available” [107] (p. 17), there are indications that part of the material from the Salomonsen collections was found at the ARS production site *Sidi Marzouk Tounsi* in Tunisia [78] (p. 41); cf. [Figure 7](#). A considerable number of further purchases were made on the art market. These acquisitions themselves were usually documented and published [110] (pp. 656–657) and the provenance of these objects was usually unclear.

Thiery, F., Veller, J., Raddatz, L., Rokohl, L., Boochs, F., & Mees, A. W. (2023). A Semi-Automatic Semantic-Model-Based Comparison Workflow for Archaeological Features on Roman Ceramics. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 12(4), 167.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi12040167>

How the RGZM go the ARS objects ...

0.39676

Weidemann 1990, 16.

53.199 Mainz, Romisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum 0.39676
LRP Form 53
Restored from fragments. Dm. 17,0 cm.
Hercules (8.107); quiver and bow (1.44); club (1.45); tree (3.30).
Zaberns Archäologische Kalender 1977, Blatt 2.-15.5.
New York (1979) no. 140.
Frankfurt (1983) no. 179.
Munich (1989) no. 207.
Mainz (1990) no. 16.

Löwenstein 2015, 461.

Armstrong 1993
A thesaurus of applied motives
on African red slip ware

Object
Biography

V. Liebler / F. Thiery, CC BY-SA 4.0

The previous practice of recording ARS pottery and its decoration involved photographs and drawings in analogue publications

Vanessa Liebler / NFDI4Objects, CC BY-SA 4.0

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortium **NFDI4Objects** aims to meet the infrastructural needs of researchers and practitioners who work on the **material remains** of around **2.6 million years** of human and environmental history to develop integrated solutions for FAIR and LOUD data across the humanities and natural sciences.

Integration into NFDI4Objects?

Capture

Step 1: Object Biography

Object
Biography

3D capturing using a structured light scanner

Creating textured 3D models as a basis for further analyses

Modelling of the 3D capturing in an ontology

Qualify

Step 2: Object Biography

Object: © LEIZA | Foto: © Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg

The Scene

The Observations

The Interpretations

Analyse

Step 3: Object Biography

Object
Biography

3,0 mm 1,5 mm 0 mm -1,5 mm -3,0 mm

Analysing the material and appliqué comparisons ...

... by creating a ruleset to calculate scores ...

39450 hare 1 hare 2

ARS3D project/i3mainz/LEIZA, CC BY-SA 4.0

hare 1	feature name	hare 2	feature name
O.39450	object name	O.39450	object name
Applique	feature type	Applique	feature type

Move the slider to change the opacity of the overlay layers of the **left windows**

Opacity Value: 64%

Move the slider to change the opacity of the overlay layer of the **right windows**

Opacity Value: 100%

... resulting in an analysing platform for researchers ...

Comparison Overall	
<i>borderline case</i>	estimation overall
No	logic process overruled
-	veto reason

Scores	
1	score overall
1	score (archaeology)

Geometric Information	
62.65 x 39.8	dimension [mm]
-1.35 to 1.89	max. height deviation range [mm]

Automatic Geometric Estimation	
<i>borderline case</i>	geometric estimation
Yes	geometric interference

Archaeological Estimation	
<i>borderline case</i>	archaeological estimation
No	global conspicuity
Yes	local conspicuity
<i>Shift or Twist (local)</i>	local conspicuity detail
Yes	same object

... visualising the result of the appliqué differences.

Currently Database “404 NOT found”... Software ist like Fish ...

Share

Step 4: Object Biography

Object
Biography

LOD

Wikibase

**“FAIR Data Object,
exchangeable”**

Data

Metadata

PID

How to share the ARS data?

Object Statement	
Hayes	
Hayes 53A	141
Hayes 56	37
Hayes 55	5
Hayes 54	5
Hayes 52B	4
Hayes 104	3
Hayes 48B	3
Hayes 82	2
Hayes 51	2
Hayes 61	2
Hayes 58B	1
Hayes 172	1
Hayes 174	1
Hayes 67	1
Hayes 1	1
Hayes 75	1
Hayes 51B	1
Atlante	
Atlante X A1a	15
Atlante VIII A2a	2
Atlante X A1c	1
Atlante VIII A1b	1
Atlante X A1b	1
Atlante X B1a	1

Hayes (1972), p. 74

Hayes (1972), p. 74

WIKIDATA Hayes 53A (Q109334933)

ceramic form in Hayes (1972), pp 78-80

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hayes 53A	ceramic form in Hayes (1972), pp 78-80	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- instance of: [typology item](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]
- work of art: (0 references) [+ add reference]
- part of: [Late Roman Pottery](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]
- [ARSD African Red Slip Ware digital](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]

WIKIDATA Hayes 56 (Q100547588)

No description defined

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hayes 56	No description defined	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- instance of: [typology item](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]
- work of art: (0 references) [+ add reference]
- part of: [Late Roman Pottery](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]
- [ARSD African Red Slip Ware digital](#) (0 references) [+ add reference]

Hic sunt dracones? Link 'em all!

archaeology.link African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Linked Open Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

bowl with Pan^{EV}

http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763

The bowl with Pan resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: **Turtle (TTL)**

Property	Value
instanceOf (amt:instanceOf)	InformationCarrier (lado:InformationCarrier) [x]
arachneEntityID (lado:arachneEntityID)	7031495 [x]
arachneModellID (lado:arachneModellID)	7031496 [x]
carries (lado:carries)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ satyr 1 (no:feat_a05c2f04-6f54-4579-ae08-7fc86c5c5ff2) ▪ satyr 2 (no:feat_addec23f-8165-41fe-9338-381eb7abdac9) ▪ satyr 3 (no:feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131bb8429)
hasConditionString (lado:hasConditionString)	reconstructed (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
hasImage (lado:hasImage)	8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763.jpg [x]
hasType (lado:hasType)	ARS_Object (lado:ARS_Object) [x]
inventoryNumber (lado:inventoryNumber)	O.39711 (RGZM) (xsd:string)
madeByString (lado:madeByString)	potter wheel (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
madeOfString (lado:madeOfString)	clay (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
number (lado:number)	1 (xmls:integer)
representedBy (lado:representedBy)	pf_c30c01b2-9c7e-45ec-833b-f734e1000016 (no:pf_c30c01b2-9c7e-45ec-833b-f734e1000016)
representedByString (lado:representedByString)	bowl (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
timeinterval (lado:timeinterval)	Late Antiquity / 310/320-430/450 AD (xsd:string)
type (rdf:type)	InformationCarrier (lado:InformationCarrier) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	bowl with Pan (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763 (xsd:string)
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	ImportPythonScript_AR53D (no:ImportPythonScript_AR53D)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	Q105268778 (wde:Q105268778) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	activity_ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763 (no:activity_ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763)

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[Impressum](#) | [Datenschutz](#)

Property	Value
depicts (lado:depicts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pan (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en) satyr (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
depictsReference (lado:depictsReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ir_31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73 (no:ir_31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73) ir_3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7 (no:ir_3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7)
hasImage (lado:hasImage)	7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429.png [x]
hasType (lado:hasType)	FeatureType_Applique (lado:FeatureType_Applique) [x]
madeByString (lado:madeByString)	applied decorated (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
selectedArea (lado:selectedArea)	feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429_geom (no:feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429_geom)
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429_geom (no:feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429_geom)
type (rdf:type)	Feature (lado:Feature) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	satyr 3 (xsd:string)
is carries (lado:carries) of	ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763 (no:ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763)
is member (rdfs:member) of	Feature Instances Collection (no:Feature_collection)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429 (xsd:string)
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	ImportPythonScript_ARS3D (no:ImportPythonScript_ARS3D)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	Q105268778 (wde:Q105268778) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	activity_feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429 (no:activity_feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429)

... showing a “Pan” feature ...

archaeology.link African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Linked Open Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

Löwenstein Pan II EN

http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ir_31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73

The Löwenstein Pan II resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
hasImage (lado:hasImage)	7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429.png [x]
hasType (lado:hasType)	Löwenstein (lado:Löwenstein) [x]
type (rdf:type)	IconographyReference (lado:IconographyReference) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	Löwenstein Pan II (xsd:string)
is member (rdfs:member) of	IconographyReference Instances Collection (lado:IconographyReference_collection)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dc:identifier)	31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73 (xsd:string)
bibliographicCitation (terms:bibliographicCitation)	Löwenstein (2015), pp. 568-569 (xsd:string)
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	ImportPythonScript_AR53D (no:ImportPythonScript_AR53D)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	Q105268778 (wde:Q105268778) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	activity_ir_31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73 (no:activity_ir_31a713d8-db33-4860-b253-5d7abc907e73)

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Figurentyp II (Armstrong Motiv 8.75) (Abb. 130)

Die Applike mit der Darstellung des Figurentyps II ist von einer bereits oben in Bezug auf den Satyr Figurentypus I und Pan Figurentyp I genannten Schale Form Hayes 53A im Römisch-Germanischen Zentralmuseum in Mainz belegt (Kat.-Nr. K 4). Sie zeigt Pan mit dem Oberkörper in Frontalansicht und den Beinen in Seitenansicht. Er steht auf einem Bein, hebt das an-

zu Löwenstein (2015), p. 713

zu Löwenstein (2015), p. 568 ff.

Armstrong (1993), pp. 184-185

8.75 *Faun(?)* Male creature with the hooves and shaggy legs of a goat and the body and bearded head of a man, with a pair of horns springing from his forehead. He is turned to the left with his head turned back in profile to the right, and lifts his hands and legs in a dancing attitude. He wears a torque with a pendant around his neck. It occurs on the floor of a complete bowl (53.211) with a naked male dancing figure (motive 8.61) and a second goat-legged creature (motive 8.74).

archaeology.link African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Linked Open Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

Armstrong 8.75 EN

http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ir_3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7

The Armstrong 8.75 resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
hasImage (lado:hasImage)	7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429.png [x]
hasType (lado:hasType)	Armstrong (lado:Armstrong) [x]
type (rdf:type)	IconographyReference (lado:IconographyReference) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	Armstrong 8.75 (xsd:string)
is member (rdfs:member) of	IconographyReference Instances Collection (no:IconographyReference_collection)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dc:identifier)	3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7 (xsd:string)
bibliographicCitation (terms:bibliographicCitation)	Armstrong (1993), pp. 184-185 (xsd:string)
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	ImportPythonScript_AR53D (no:ImportPythonScript_AR53D)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	Q105268778 (wde:Q105268778) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	activity_ir_3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7 (no:activity_ir_3d364d46-fd0a-45f4-8be9-f13cd53505e7)

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... described in the literature ...

Item Discussion

Löwenstein K / FT II (Pan) (Q123668582)

iconographic description in Löwenstein (2015), pp.568-569 [edit](#)

▼ In more languages [Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Löwenstein K / FT II (Pan)	iconographic description in Löwenstein (2015), pp.568-569	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of [edit](#)

Q110892439 iconographic item

[+ add reference](#)

▼ 0 references

work of art [edit](#)

Q110892439 work of art

[+ add reference](#)

▼ 0 references

[+ add value](#)

part of [edit](#)

Q110892439 Mythologische Darstellungen auf Gebrauchsgegenständen der Spätantike. Die appliken- und reliefverzierte Sigillata C3/C4

[+ add reference](#)

▼ 0 references

African Red Slip Ware digital (ARS3D) [edit](#)

Q110892439 African Red Slip Ware digital (ARS3D)

[+ add reference](#)

▼ 0 references

... and in Wikidata.

Published as LOD via the data hub archaeology.link

Interlink

Step 5: Object Biography

Object
Biography

ChronOntology

Wikidata

Arachne (iDAI.objects)

LEIZA Databases

ARS3D

Creating a LOD network with archaeology.link, iDAI.world and Wikidata ...

... to be part of the Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem ...

A collection is an individual set of research data imported into the knowledge graph. Each collection is identified by

Information about collections is stored in the RDF graph <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>.

Table Response 16 results

	collection	name
1	n4oc:2	Paläontologischen Sammlung der FAU Geowissenschaftliche Sammlung der FAU
2	n4oc:1	Ur- und Frühgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU
3	n4oc:6	Schulgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU und Schulmuseum
4	n4oc:5	Medizinische Sammlung der FAU
5	n4oc:3	Graphische Sammlung der FAU
6	n4oc:4	Musikinstrumentensammlung der FAU
7	n4oc:14	Kommentierte Online-Edition der fünf Reisetagebücher Hans Posses (1939 -1942)
8	n4oc:15	Corpus Vitrearum Medii Aevi Deutschland
9	n4oc:7	KENOM Virtuelles Münzportal (via LIDO)
10	n4oc:8	Samian Research Database
11	n4oc:9	Linked Open Ogham
12	n4oc:10	African Red Slip Ware
13	n4oc:11	Digitale Sammlungen der Museen der Klassikstiftung Weimar
14	n4oc:12	Graphische Sammlung des Germanisches Nationalmuseums
15	n4oc:13	KENOM (via Nomisma) via https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/
16	n4oc:16	Berliner Kunstammer

African Red Slip Ware

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10>

Loaded into the graph at 2025-11-06T12:40:33 with 64531 triples. See [import report](#).

Homepage/URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751>

Quell-Repository: ???

Lizenz der Daten: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please use SPARQL to get more information [about the collection](#) such as [used classes](#) and [used properties](#).

```
@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j.2: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j.4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10> a j.4:Database,
dcat:Dataset ;
dcterms:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
dcterms:issued "2025-11-06T12:40:33"^^xsd:dateTime ;
dcterms:license "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" ;
j.2:name "African Red Slip Ware" ;
skos:notation "10" ;
dcat:distribution [ dcterms:format <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES> ;
dcterms:issued "2025-11-06T12:40:33"^^xsd:dateTime ;
dcat:accessURL <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10> ;
dcat:downloadURL <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10/stage/collection-10.nt> ;
dcat:mediaType <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples> ] ;
foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751> .
```

... and the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph.

Remaining Challenges

Still work to do ...

Wikidata Search Wikidata Search

Pan (Q132582) Item Discussion Read

Greek god of the mountain wilds, shepherds, flocks, rustic music, fertility, spring, and theatrical criticism, with the hindquarters, legs, and horns of a goat

Language | **Label** | **Description** | **Also known as**

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	-	
English	Pan	Greek god of the mountain wilds, shepherds, flocks, rustic music, fertility, spring, and theatrical criticism, with the hindquarters, legs, and horns of a goat	
German	Pan	griechische Gottheit der Hirten	
French	Pan	divinité de la mythologie grecque de la nature, protecteur des bergers et des troupeaux, souvent représenté comme une créature chimérique, mi-homme mi-bouc	Dieu Pan
Bavarian	Pan	No description defined	

Statements

instance of Greek deity 0 references + add reference

nature deity 0 references + add reference

image 1 reference + add value

sex or gender male 0 references + add reference

Image via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q132582>

skos:closeMatch?

9 - Classical Mythology and Ancient History

92 - gods - classical mythology

92L - gods of the earth and fertility -- life in mountains and woods

92L5 - (story of) Pan

92L571 - specific aspects, allegorical aspects of Pan: Pan as patron

92L571 Pan-herm

Search with these related keywords:
Pan, ancient history, gods, patron, fertility, allegory, mountain, earth, classical antiquity, forest, herm, history, mythology, Pan-herm

Also see:
92L671 - Priapus-herm

Add more detail:
92L571(+0) - variant

Here are 20 sample images.

Research

Cultural Objects Names Authority® Iconography Display

ID: 901001072
Page link: <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/ia/901001072>

Pan (Greek deity)

Note: [In Greek mythology, a fertility deity, more or less bestial in form, he was associated by the Romans with Faunus. Originally an Arcadian deity, his name is a Doric contraction of paen ("pasture") but was commonly supposed in antiquity to be connected with pan ("all"). His father was usually said to be Hermes, but a comic invention held that he was the product of an orgy of Olympus's wife Hera with her many suitors. Pan was generally represented as a vigorous and lustful figure having the horns, legs, and ears of a goat; in later art the human parts of his form were much more emphasized. He haunted the high hills, and his chief concern was with flocks and herds, not with agriculture.]

Names:
Pan (Greek deity) (preferred,English-9,D,N)
Πάν (Greek deity) (Greek,U,N)

Hierarchical Position:
Legend, Religion, Mythology (P)
.....Greek iconography (9)
.....Greek characters (G)
.....Pan (Greek deity) (I)

Related Iconography:
is actor for ... Pan and Syrinx [901000648]
.....Legend, Religion, Mythology, Greek iconography, Greek narratives, Pan and Syrinx (Greco-Roman narrative)
associated with ... Syrinx [901000489]
child of ... Hermes [901000489]
.....Legend, Religion, Mythology, Greek iconography, Greek characters, Syrinx (Greek nymph)
counterpart is ... Faunus [901000721]
.....Legend, Religion, Mythology, Roman iconography, Roman characters, Faunus (Ancient Italian deity)
[901001947]

Other Relationships:
role/characteristic is ... deity
.....(people in religion, people in religion and related occupations, people in the humanities, people by occupation, people (agents), People (hierarchy name)) (AAT)
culture/religion is ... Ancient Greek (culture or style)
.....(Aegean periods, Aegean, Mediterranean (Early Western World), Early Western World, styles, periods, and cultures by region, Styles and Periods (hierarchy name)) (AAT)
deity of ... Iuul
.....(negative emotions, emotion, psychological concepts, social science concepts, Associated Concepts (hierarchy name)) (AAT)
deity of ... fertility
.....(biological concepts, scientific concepts, Associated Concepts (hierarchy name)) (AAT)

Image via <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/ia/901001072>

How to model fuzziness and uncertainty?

How to align different research traditions?

How may it look like in ARS? (ChaptGPT's idea...)

The CeraTyOnt ontology might help...

Outlook

Why is it worth it...

(Examples from Samian Ware)


```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX lido: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX amt: <http://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab#>
PREFIX samian: <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/>

SELECT ?subject ?subjectLabel ?predicateLabel ?objectLabel ?weight WHERE {
  ?subject lido:hasAMT ?amt.
  ?amt rdfs:subject ?subject.
  ?subject rdfs:label ?subjectLabel.
  ?predicate rdfs:label ?predicateLabel.
  ?amt rdfs:object ?object.
  ?object rdfs:label ?objectLabel.
  ?amt amt:weight ?weight.
  FILTER(?subject = samian:ic_118117)
  FILTER(?predicate = lido:representedBy)
  FILTER (lang(?predicateLabel) = 'en')
}

```

Output:

subject	subjectLabel	predicateLabel	objectLabel	weight
samian:ic_118117	"redipossel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"15/17"	0.330000013
samian:ic_118117	"redipossel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"18"	0.330000013
samian:ic_118117	"redipossel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"18/31"	0.330000013

-> The Informationcarriers either has the potform 15/17, 18 OR 18/31 (vagueness), so each weight results in 0.33

Samian ID: 14264 Potter/Die: Abitus (Habitus) 1a Site: London (Londinium) Findspot: --- Plelades ID: 79374 WGS84: 51.512720 -0.091840 OFABITI	Samian ID: 16902 Potter/Die: Albanus ii; 1b Site: London (Londinium) Findspot: --- Plelades ID: 79393 WGS84: 51.512790 -0.091840 OFABAI I	Samian ID: 133992 Potter/Die: Severianus i; 7a Site: London (Londinium) Findspot: Shadwell, docks Plelades ID: 79393 WGS84: 51.512790 -0.091840 SEVERIANI
Samian ID: 16570 Potter/Die: Agedillus ii; 1b Site: Southwark Findspot: London Bridge Plelades ID: --- WGS84: 51.500000 -0.089160 AGEDILLII	Samian ID: 38576 Potter/Die: Calvus i; 5gg Site: Southwark Findspot: London Bridge Plelades ID: --- WGS84: 51.500000 -0.089160 OF-CALVI	Samian ID: 36233 Potter/Die: Batrio; 1a Site: Southwark Findspot: North End Southwark Bridge Plelades ID: --- WGS84: 51.500000 -0.089160 BVTRIO

Mees, A. W., & Thiery, F. (2026). Bridging Archaeological Samian Ware Data and the Knowledge Graph: Potentials and Challenges of Using Wikidata as a Linking Hub. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 12(16), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.427>

I know the issues in ARS, however why is it worth it ...

Thiery, F., & Mees, A. W. (2025). Dating Dated Sites: Using Correspondence Analysis to handle Chronologies as Graphs. *Journal of Historical Network Research*, 12(1).
<https://doi.org/10.25517/jhnr.v12i1.105>

Fig. 4 Example of temporal reasoning using four Limes sections. Graphic: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Fig. 10 CA Result. Graphic: Florian Thiery/Allard W. Mees, CC BY 4.0

Fig. 6 Alligator method test of Roman emperors, result as a virtual timeline. Graphic: Florian Thiery/Allard W. Mees, CC BY 4.0

Fig. 7 Alligator method test of Roman emperors, result as a relative chronology. Graphic: Florian Thiery/Allard W. Mees, CC BY 4.0

Fig. 11 A: The AMT time ontology using Allen's interval algebra. B: AMT Axiom to perform reasoning using the during and after intervals and the product logic. C: Exemplary AMT modeling with the AMT web tool (cf. <https://leiza-scit.github.io/amt-limes/>). D: Exemplary AMT reasoning with the AMT web tool. Graphic: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0

... also for dealing with (relative) chronologies.

EAA 2019
Session 162 Culture contacts in the western Mediterranean sea during the Roman Age.
Pottery as cultural marker between traffics and local productions

African Red Slip ware in Sicily during the Roman empire and the Late Antiquity : the region of Agrigento and Termini Imerese.

Fabrizio Ducati*
Claudio Capelli**

* Università degli Studi di Palermo; Aix Marseille Univ, CNRS, CCI, Aix-en-Provence, France
** DISTAV, Università degli Studi di Genova

The integrated approach: archaeology and archaeometry

From BONIFAY 2004, Pl II, n. 11.

D1
Atelier d'El Mahrine
Hayes 67

From BONIFAY 2016, pp. 557-558; CAPELLI *et alii* 2016, p. 384, fig. 81.

From MACKENSEN, SCHNEIDER 2002, fig. 14-15.

Publish the archaeometric and petrographic analysis as LOD?

Provenance Studies on Ancient Pottery in the Mediterranean

FACEM » BNAP-A-11

project search maps impressum

Distribution of fabric type "BNAP-A-11"

object data fabric description archaeometry petrography

sample no	M 160/2
	★ representative sample for BNAP-A-11
fabric type	BNAP-A-11
supposed site of production	Bay of Naples
sample taken	June 2011
Context Data	
site of discovery	Rome scavo del Palatino nord-orientale
registration code of context	PNE OSII 2674
Object	
ware	Transport Amphorae
object form	Amphora
object type	Dressel 2 - 4
chronology of object	Roman 1st c. AD.
fragmentation	fragmentation not specified

Cite this page as: FACEM - <http://facem.at/bnap-a-11>

Provenance Studies on Ancient Pottery in the Mediterranean

FACEM » BNAP-A-11

project search maps impressum

Distribution of fabric type "BNAP-A-11"

object data fabric description archaeometry petrography

Visual Examination of Fresh Break	
visual examination of fresh break	red, granular, many small and medium sized white and dark inclusions
colour of fresh break	2.5YR 5/6
texture of fresh break	granular
hardness	hard
Observation Under the Binocular Microscope <small>(all lengths in mm)</small>	
porosity	2.5%; void form: plains; void length: 0.025-1
inclusions	35%, length: 0.025-1.25
sorting	bimodal: poorly-sorted sand in well-sorted silt
Inclusions <small>(all lengths in mm)</small>	
black inclusions	very frequent, angular, spherical; elongate, black, 0.025-0.75
calciumcarbonate	frequent, rounded, spherical, white, 0.025-0.75
carbonate pseudomorphoses	frequent, rounded, spherical, white, 0.025-0.5
foraminifera	infrequent, rounded, spherical, white, 0.025-0.5
mica	singular, angular, spherical, white, 0.025-0.125
more inclusions2	singular, angular, spherical; elongate, light brown, 0.025-0.25
more inclusions3	singular, angular, spherical; elongate, green, 0.025-0.25
quartz	infrequent, subangular, subspherical, clear, 0.025-0.5
reddish inclusions	infrequent, subrounded, subspherical, reddish brown, 0.025-1.25

Cite this page as: FACEM - <http://facem.at/bnap-a-11>

There are 2 more samples assigned to fabric type "BNAP-A-11": [Show All](#)

Pottery Production in the Bay of Naples: Problems, History of Research and Current Methods: For more than a thousand years the Bay of Naples was not only one of the most important and dynamic areas of the antique Mediterranean, but also a region well known for its production of pottery.

Fabrics of Western Greek Amphorae from Campania and from the Bay of Naples: IntroductionIn the last decennium our knowledge of the pottery production in the Bay of Naples has increased significantly and this is also valid for the production of transport amphorae. Of particular importance is the monographic study of Hellenistic amphorae from Ischia and from a series of shipwrecks ...

Anfore e ceramiche aoroma dall'evamposto militare di Monte Turci (CT). Uno studio preliminare


```

@prefix bfo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> .
@prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
@prefix crmsci: <http://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/CRMsci/> .
@prefix facemv: <http://facem.at/vocab/> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<http://facem.at/entity/graph_bnap_a_11> a prov:Entity ;
  rdfs:comment "Auto-generated by facem_pipeline.py from FACEM HTML" ;
  prov:generatedAtTime "2026-03-20T12:57:19.370942+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  prov:wasDerivedFrom <https://facem.at/bnap-a-11/> .

<http://facem.at/entity/observation_binocular_bnap_a_11_sample> a facemv:BinocularObservation,
  crmsci:S4_Observation ;
  rdfs:label "Binocular stereoscope observation of BNAP-A-11-sample" ;
  crmsci:O8_observed <http://facem.at/entity/sample_bnap_a_11_sample> .

<http://facem.at/ontology/> a owl:Ontology .

<http://facem.at/entity/object_bnap_a_11_sample> a facemv:CeramicObject,
  crm:E22_Human_Made_Object ;
  rdfs:label "BNAP-A-11-sample" ;
  facemv:hasFabricType <http://facem.at/entity/fabric_bnap_a_11/> ;
  facemv:hasSample <http://facem.at/entity/sample_bnap_a_11_sample/> ;
  crm:P45_consists_of <http://facem.at/entity/fabric_bnap_a_11/> .

<http://facem.at/entity/fabric_bnap_a_11/> a facemv:FabricType,
  bfo:BFO_0000040,
  crm:E57_Material ;
  rdfs:label "BNAP-A-11" ;
  rdfs:seeAlso <https://facem.at/bnap-a-11/> ;
  skos:notation "BNAP-A-11" .

<http://facem.at/entity/sample_bnap_a_11_sample/> a facemv:CeramicSample,
  bfo:BFO_0000040,
  crmsci:S10_Material_Substantial ;
  rdfs:label "Sample BNAP-A-11-sample" ;
  crm:P46i_forms_part_of <http://facem.at/entity/object_bnap_a_11_sample/> .
  
```


FACEM as Linked Open Data to interlink Knowledge?

Thank you!
Bedankt!
Merci!

Questions?

image created using Google's Gemini

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